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ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION

Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich
PhD

Abstract. The article examines the economic content of intangible assets in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT), the peculiarities of their recognition, and a comparative analysis of approaches in foreign and national accounting standards.

Keywords: intangible assets, information and communication technologies, accounting, IFRS-38, IFRS-7, recognition, identification, goodwill, research and development costs.

INTRODUCTION

Digitalization processes taking place in the world, the strengthening of innovative approaches and the expansion of the market of intellectual products are radically increasing the importance of intangible assets in the activities of economic entities. In particular, in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT), intangible assets are considered the main resource that determines the company's competitive advantage, customer base and product quality.¹ Therefore, the issue of correct understanding of the economic content of intangible assets and their reliable reflection in financial statements remains relevant for enterprises operating in this field.

The development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets specific goals to increase the volume of industrial production by 1.4 times.² In implementing these tasks, business entities are directly related to the creation of new types of products, varieties and services, which, in turn, is directly related to the creation of intangible assets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

F.T. Abduvakhidov, I.N. Kuziev, and Sh.Kh. Dadabaev (2019) expressed the following views on intangible assets, namely: Intangible assets are identifiable property objects that an enterprise retains for the purpose of producing products (works, services) or selling products or for performing administrative or other functions over a long period of time, and that do not have tangible substance.

U.I. Inoyatov, S.D. Yusupov and F.R. Salimbekova (2011) discussed intangible assets as follows: Intangible assets are objects that do not have tangible substance and are controlled by an economic entity for a long period of time (for use or management of more than 1 year). Intangible assets include the right to use land, water and other natural resources, patents, know-how, goodwill (firm value), organizational costs incurred during the establishment of the enterprise, copyrights, rights to industrial designs, software products for electronic computers and other intangible assets.

G.Q. Turaeva B.E. Matrasulov S.I. Matkulieva A.A. Abduvohidov A.B. Mukhametov (2023) stated the following in their works on the organization of the account of intangible assets: Intangible assets, along with fixed assets, are objects of long-term investments and are considered part of depreciable assets, and their

1 According to world statistics, the share of these expenses in the gross domestic product in the leading countries in terms of research and development costs is more than 3 percent. Source: www.worldstatistics.com

2 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". www.lex.uz

accounting largely corresponds to the accounting of fixed assets. The main rules for accounting for intangible assets are the procedure for determining the time of recognition (recognition), estimating the balance sheet value and useful life, determining the methods for calculating depreciation, estimating and accounting for other changes in the balance sheet value and determining the financial results from their disposal, as well as the procedure for disclosing information on them in financial statements.

Economist N. Toshmamatov (2019) defined intangible assets as follows: Intangible assets are the rights of an enterprise, capital investment projects that have value for the enterprise but cannot be seen or touched, such as trademarks, patents, and other similar rights.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scientific methods such as scientific abstraction, induction and deduction, historical-logical, comparative analysis, systematic approach and generalization were used in this research work.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to International Financial Reporting Standard BHXS-38 entitled “Intangible Assets”, an asset is a resource controlled by an organization as a result of past events and from which economic benefits are expected in the future.³ In this standard, an intangible asset is defined as “an identifiable non-monetary asset that does not have a tangible substance.” Here, the criterion of identifiability is important, because this criterion is the main characteristic that distinguishes an intangible asset from goodwill.

According to the national accounting standard, IFRS-7 defines intangible assets as “identifiable assets that do not have tangible substance and are held for use in the production or provision of services over a three-year period.”⁴ Comparatively, the national standard differs from the international standard in that it clearly states the concept of “specific period” (more than one year).

The definitions of economists reflect different approaches. R. Dosmuratov (Dosmuratov, 2007) emphasizes the methodology of accounting and auditing intangible assets, while I. Ochilov and J. Kurbanboev (Ochilov and Kurbanboev, 2007) represent them as objects of intellectual property. According to F. Gulomava (Gulomova, 2000), intangible assets include “objects that do not have a physical or material form and create the possibility of generating additional income”. Sh. Ilhamov (Ilhamov, 2005) emphasizes the importance of determining their quantitative limits.

Based on the given definitions, the following author’s definition is given to intangible assets by the author:

“Intangible assets are values that do not have a material nature and will benefit the business entity in the future.”

There are three main criteria for recognizing intangible assets: (1) identifiability; (2) control over the resource; and (3) expectation of future economic benefits. If all of these criteria are not met, they are recognized as an expense and reflected in the statement of financial performance instead of being recognized as an asset.

The specific features of intangible assets in the ICT sector are as follows: first, software products, production secrets (know-how), and intellectual property objects are important strategic resources for the industry; second, the creation of these assets is carried out using more internal resources, which is closely related to the calculation of research and development costs; third, some of the assets (for example, software) may be in tangible form (disk, flash card), but are considered intangible in economic essence.

Foreign experience has shown that US financial accounting standards are developed by the FASB in accordance with USGAAP requirements, including FAS 142-3, EITF 08-7, and Rules No. 141R.⁵ In the Russian Federation, the regulation of PBU 14/2007 “Intangible assets” is applied, and according to it, the value of intangible assets is determined based on actual costs⁶. These foreign approaches are broader and more detailed than the national standard and involve the use of revaluation models and impairment testing.

According to the financial statements of the research object, Uzbekistan Post JSC for 2019–2023, the total assets of this enterprise amounted to 129,189 million soums in 2019, but by 2023 they had increased to 303,703 million soums. During this period, the value of intangible assets increased from 20.6 million soums to 4,864.0 million soums. Although this represents a significant increase in absolute terms, its share in the total assets structure reached only 2 percent.⁷ In the first four years (2019–2022), the share of intangible assets

3 IAS 38 “Intangible Assets” (IAS 38). <https://www.iasplus.com/en/standards/ias/ias38>

4 IAS No. 7, “Intangible Assets,” approved by the Order of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 35 dated March 25, 2005. lex.uz/acts/-828581

5 FSP FAS 142-3 (As Issued). https://www.fasb.org/pdf/fsp_fas142-3.pdf

6 Polozhenie po bukhhalterskomu uchyotu “Uchyot nematerialnyx aktivov” PBU 14/2007. RF Ministry of Finance, 27.12.2007 No. 153n.

7 Calculated by the author based on the financial statements of Uzbekistan Post JSC for 2019–2023.

was almost 0 percent, which indicates the slow participation of the enterprise in digitization and innovation processes.

This analysis shows that the intangible assets portfolio of Uzbekistan Post, a JSC operating in the ICT sector, is relatively low. This situation can be explained by three reasons: (a) the fact that software and developments created by the enterprise are recorded as research and development costs and subsequently do not meet the criteria for capitalization; (b) the accounting policy does not clearly define the criteria for recognizing intangible assets; (c) methodological shortcomings in separating labor and other costs from research costs.

Objects that are part of intangible assets are classified according to various criteria. According to the first criterion, they can be divided into such types as (a) patents and licenses; (b) copyrights; (c) brand names and trademarks; (d) franchises; (e) goodwill. According to the second criterion (according to the method of occurrence), they are divided into two types: those obtained from other persons and those created using internal resources. According to the third criterion (according to the useful life), they are distinguished into intangible assets with a definite term and those with an indefinite term.

According to the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, intangible assets are legally divided into such types as copyright, related rights, industrial property rights, rights to new varieties of plants and animals, and rights of participants in civil transactions (company name, trademark).⁸ The proposed procedure of legal protection will have specific characteristics depending on the type of intangible asset.

In particular, the most widespread intangible assets in the ICT sector are software, databases, trade secrets (know-how), intellectual property rights, and franchise relationships. When forming accounting policies for their identification and recognition, it is appropriate to require the following conditions to be met in combination:

- non-existence of the object in material form;
- possibility to identify the object separately (separated from other assets);
- control of the economic entity over the object;
- estimation of future economic benefits;
- useful service period exceeding one year;
- the object's value can be reliably measured.

An item can only be recognized as an intangible asset if all of the above criteria are met. Otherwise, the costs incurred to acquire or create the item are recognized as an expense when they are incurred.

The specific features of the process of creating intangible assets in the ICT sector are as follows. First, the creation of objects in this area is often carried out using internal resources (in particular, the development of software products, the creation of databases). Second, the process is long-term (several months or years), which requires the distribution of costs over a period of years. Third, it is difficult to distinguish between the research and development stages, since their accounting treatment is significantly different: research costs are capitalized in the income statement, while development costs are capitalized as assets.

According to IAS 38, for development costs to be recognized as intangible assets, all of the following conditions must be met: (1) the technical feasibility of completing the item; (2) the intention to complete the item and use or sell it; (3) the existence of a path to obtain economic benefits from the item; (4) the availability of necessary financial and other resources; (5) the ability to reliably measure the development costs.⁹ If any of these criteria are not met, the object is not capitalized as an intangible asset.

Taking the example of the object of the study, JSC "Uzbekistan Post", the enterprise is currently engaged in work related to the development of software (in particular, postal services automation systems, customer base applications). However, the analysis showed that the lack of a clear separation of research and development stages for this work, and the lack of criteria for capitalization of costs, leads to the fact that the value of existing intangible assets is lower than their true economic value.

A comparative analysis of IFRS-38 and IFRS-7 revealed the following differences. First, the international standard allows the use of a revaluation model (if there is an active market), while the national standard does not cover this issue in detail. Second, the international standard requires an impairment test, while the national standard poorly covers this issue. Third, the international standard allows for indefinite-lived intangible assets not to be amortized, while the national standard differs in this regard.

Therefore, additional measures should be taken to harmonize the national standard with international standards. In particular, it is appropriate to include the following items in BHMS-7: (a) defining the revaluation model of intangible assets; (b) prescribing the procedure for carrying out the impairment test; (v) characteristics of the amortization regime for indefinite-lived intangible assets.

8 Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Part 4, Chapter 70). www.lex.uz

9 IAS 38 "Intangible Assets", paragraph 57. London: IFRS Foundation, 2014.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the research, the following conclusions and proposals were formed.

Firstly, intangible assets in the ICT sector have a unique meaning as the main strategic resource of business entities, and when recognizing them, it is necessary to take into account the differences between international and national standards.

Secondly, the definition proposed by the author, "Intangible assets are non-tangible values that will benefit the business entity in the future" differs from the existing definitions and distinguishes the future economic value as the main criterion.

Thirdly, the two-pronged approach proposed by the author to classify intangible assets (acquired from other persons and created using internal business resources) is of practical importance for business entities, since the accounting methods for both categories differ significantly from each other.

Fourth, we recommend that enterprises operating in the ICT sector include criteria for recognizing intangible assets, clear algorithms for recognition, and primary document forms in their accounting policies. The implementation of this proposal will increase the reliability of financial statements for users.

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